

FORMAL COMPARISON OF TEXT AND DISCOURSE

SEVINJ ISMAYILOVA

Institute of Linguistics named after Nasimi of ANAS

Department of Sociolinguistics and Psycholinguistics

junior researcher,

Ph.D student

Summary

Text linguistics, one of the actual fields of linguistics in modern times, appeared in the 1920s. Nevertheless, we can say that the history of the text is as old as the history of mankind. Today, after the emergence of the concept of discourse, which is an integral element of modern text linguistics, the terms text and discourse were distinguished, some linguists considered them the same thing, and some noted that they are completely different concepts. We also agree with the latter, and in this study, the concepts of text-discourse have been formally compared, and the different features between them have been noted.

Keywords: text, discourse, element of reality, context, condition.

When analyzing different scientific sources, we come to the conclusion that discourse and text are quite different concepts. It is well-known that a person's need for communication is usually met by oral speech. Oral speech forms in the result of discourse. But discourse is not just speech. The real situation in which the communication process takes place, that is, not only the mood of the speaker and his interlocutor, but also the feelings of the random participants in the communication, plays a role in the formation of such a discourse.

In order to distinguish discourse more precisely from both oral and written text, it is necessary to accept the first of them, that is, the discourse as a process, and the oral or written text as a result. Discourse is an activity,

that is, an active process, and the text is a completed constant result. While the discourse covers the cognitive, linguo-social field, the text belongs to the purely linguistic field

Teun A van Dijk characterizes the distinction between text and discourse in this way: Discourse is an actual being spoken text and is an abstract grammatical structure of what is called “text”. While discourse is a concept related to speech, actual speech activity, “text” is a concept related to the language system, formal linguistic knowledge, linguistic competence [1, 77].

It is sometimes considered that discourse is a linguistic phenomenon that realizes in a text. For realizing the discourse, it is important to have text, condition as well as context. Discourse takes place not in space as in communication, but in a constantly interactive process between the participants of communication under certain conditions. N. Enkvist noted this in his classic definition of discourse: “Discourse is the unity of the text and the context with a social component” [2, 132]. In this definition, Enkvist emphasizes the importance of not only the text and context, but also the social component, social experience and also condition.

From the point of view of Mayil B. Asgarov’s “Theory of Linguo-Psychological Unity”, discourse is an abstract imagination or system of psychological images formed in the human brain. It reflects a real life happened in a single time interval and a single space [3, 255]. As researcher M. Abdullayeva rightly points out, based on this theory, discourse is the first ranking element of reality in speech (Er_1). In other words, it is a psychological image that is formed in the human brain as a result of the perception of speech and has the essence of abstract imagination. At the same time, it is the initial thought, purpose, or goal that gives rise to speech. The second ranking element of reality of speech (Er_2) is a complex of linguistic structural units formed as a result of the reflection of discourse in the language system, i.e. the text.

During the research, we come to the conclusion that discourse and text cannot be separated from each other, but it is a big mistake to consider them the same thing. Contrary to some researchers, we believe that discourse does not and cannot realize in the text, but realizes through the text. Discourse is a broader type of activity that combines a process and an outcome in itself that develops over time and space. The text is formed on the basis of distant contact in terms of space and time. The text itself gives the impression that the active and passive communicator is completely deprived of visual, vocal and other opportunities to communicate with each other. That is why in modern times the term “discourse” has gone beyond the boundaries of text linguistics.

LITERATURE:

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